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Fully automated piping in an Airbus A320 landing gear bay using graph-based design languages

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Abstract. System design in an aircraft is still a costly, manual and iterative approach. One major cost driver of changes in system installation are design efforts for creating new pipes in an earlier stage and the costs accumulated during the in service life. To reduce these costs and the time to market, an automation approach with an integrated design optimization encoded in graph-based design languages and executable in a design compiler is proposed.

To generate the pipe work automatically, a set of input data (e.g. start- and end-points of a pipe with tangents and fixing positions) is given by the user. It also contains, among others, the weightings for the optimization criteria (e.g. length of the pipe resp. the weight vs. the number of bends) to influence the evaluation of the generated pipes and thereby the final solution. As an initial step in the automatic pipe generation process, a route through the installation space is searched. Subsequently, the installation space is simplified and a respective minimal distance to each obstacle which a pipe should satisfy is added. Then for each pipe an initial solution is estimated and each pipe is optimized by a simulated annealing algorithm. At last, all given requirements are automatically verified. The capabilities of the newly developed automated piping are demonstrated on the pipe work in an Airbus A320 landing gear bay.

1. Introduction

Thematic Motivation. With increasing complexity of aircraft systems the design cost to modify or introduce pipes in an existing aircraft increases. The reason for this is that aircraft systems are mostly routed in the same areas, that segregation and clearances are at their limits, that the access and installation sequences need to be considered from the beginning and that the modification of one system should not lead to a cascading change in other systems.

Aircraft systems and pipe work are impacted by several design evolutions during the life-cycle of an airplane. From the first design to the subsequent iterative incremental modifications during its service life the routing of aircraft systems has to be created, modified and adapted several times in an aircraft life to meet the latest aviation requirements and manufacturing technologies or to incorporate design improvements or corrections.

Furthermore, design trades for the overall optimization of a future aircraft must consider different architectures and locations of new equipment and pipe routing. Current pipe work is a manual process of routing the pipe through the installation area, while taking into account all clearances, manufacturing and installation requirements. All these attempts increase the non-recurring cost of every change, thus reduces the profit for the aircraft manufacturer. Aircraft manufacturer are therefore constantly looking for optimization and automation of the pipe design process.

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The series solution of the pipe work in an Airbus A320 mounting rack can be seen in figure 1 as an illustrative example of the typical complexity in an aircraft pipe network installation.

Figure 1: Airbus A320 series solution mounting rack (© 2021 Airbus)

Manufacturing technology influence. The pipes generated by the proposed algorithm should be able to be manufactured with the rotary draw bending process for bending machines described in *VDI 3430* [1]. In this process, only bends with a fixed bending radius can be bent. The bending angle can vary within a certain range determined by the specific bending machine in use. Between two bends, a straight pipe with a minimum length has to be placed. This leads to an alternating order of straights and bends. As a result of the construction of the bending machine, a minimal distance between the bends must be established if the bends should be bent independently. Furthermore, a limited, machine depending number of bending jaws can be used to manufacture two bends with a smaller straight distance in between.

Design process influence. Both the start- and the end-points with their respective directions (i.e. the tangents), the pipe diameter and the properties of the intended bending machine must be known in advance. Also minimal distances of the pipes to certain obstacles and to each other that must be adhered to, can be set. Furthermore, a user is able to affect the piping algorithm by modifying the weighting of the different evaluation factors which will be described in more detail in section 3.1.

2. Preparation for pipe routing

Different preprocessing steps are necessary. In figure 2 an overview of the process is shown. The shown geometry is subsequently used to demonstrate the process.

2.1. Paths through the installation space

A routing from the desired beginning to the desired end of the pipe is required. To accomplish this task an existing plugin for wire harness design [2] is used, which is part of the industrial *DesignCockpit43*[®] software suite [3]. This plugin uses an A* algorithm and a collision detection to find the shortest route through an obstacle landscape under consideration of a wire diameter and a minimum bending radius. The result of the wire harness routing is shown in figure 2b.

2.2. Boundary exploration for simplified obstacle geometry

As the dependency between the complexity of the installation space geometry and the run time of the algorithm described in this paper should be small, a method called ‘ray tests’ to reduce the obstacle geometry to the relevant information was developed. Along the path, in equidistant distances, planes orthogonal to the path are created through the installation space. On every plane rays are shot from the point where the path cuts the plane in a regular star shape. The points, where the rays collide with the obstacle geometry, are stored. If an additional (potentially

Figure 2: Exemplary installation space: Airbus A320 mounting rack

individualized) margin d_m shall be applied, this margin is imposed on the geometry in advance to the ray tests. The mounting rack with a applied margin is shown in figure 3. This ensures that the rays hit the correct, expanded geometry. The points are connected to a polygon and the polygons are connected one after another to form a hose.

2.3. Definition of a pipe path

As a result of the used manufacturing technology described in section 1, the pipe path is defined as a rounded polyline with fixed arc radii. The position of the points of the polyline define the pipe path. The first and the last point of the polyline will be considered as the start- and the end-point of the pipe respectively. If a pipe is fixed by predefined fixings, the pipe is divided into independent paths between the fixings and the paths are combined together into one single pipe definition after the optimization runs have terminated.

Figure 3: Airbus A320 mounting rack geometry with margin

2.4. Estimation of polyline points

For an initial solution the positions of the points of the polyline must be estimated. All points, except the first and the last two, can be positioned in the three space dimensions. The algorithm must ensure that the distance between two following points is big enough that the bending radius can be applied and that the minimal distance between two bends required by the manufacturing technology can be fulfilled. Similarly, the first and last point are fixed and the next respectively the previous point must be on a straight line with the desired start and end tangents.

The number of polyline points is related to the number of bends. The user decides how many bends should be used at least and at most. For every number of bends in this range a pipe path must be initialized. The positions of the points for a given number of bends is estimated under the use of a path through the original installation space and the simplified installation space.

2.5. Selection of depending paths

The distance between the simplified obstacle geometries for each pipe (see section 2.2) is calculated approximately. If the distance is smaller than the allowed distance between two pipes it is possible that the pipes could intersect or be too close to each other. Therefore these pipes cannot be generated independently. As a result of this, for all depending pipe segments all combinations of estimated paths are computed. This leads to a list which pipe combinations can be optimized independently.

3. Generation and optimization of the pipes

The estimated pipe paths (see section 2.4) fulfill the requirements imposed by the manufacturing constraints described in section 1. There exist multiple criteria, which makes a trade-off necessary. These criteria need to be weighted by a user, depending on the problem specific needs, to get one specific value which describes the overall quality of the pipe path. The pipe paths are optimized based on a evaluation function by modifying the points of the polylines which describe the pipes.

3.1. Evaluation function and evaluation criteria

To get one specific value $v_n \geq 0$ in every iteration step n describing the quality of the pipe path, an evaluation function is needed. A smaller value v_n stands for a better pipe path.

$$v_n = \sum_i w_i (v_{n,i} + 1)^{k_i} \quad (1)$$

For each evaluation criteria a value $v_{n,i} \geq 0$ is calculated. As different criteria shall be combined, $v_{n,i}$ needs to be dimensionless. Referring to the method of least squares the value is raised to a specific power $k_i \geq 1$. Using $k_i > 1$ in combination with a $0 < v_{n,i} < 1$ would lead to a better evaluation than with $k_i = 1$. In order to prevent this, the term is modified, which leads to $(v_{n,i} + 1)^{k_i} \geq 1$. The result of this term can be weighted by a factor w_i which is chosen by a user. There are the following evaluation criteria available:

- Length of pipe
- Aperture of bends
- Number of bends
- Boundary violation
- Distance to center line¹
- Distance to the path through the installation space²
- Minimal distance between two bends

¹ In every plane the center of a circle is calculated which has the largest radius that fits inside the boundary polygon (see section 2.2). The circle center points are calculated with the algorithm proposed by *Garcia-Castellanos and Lombardo (2007)* [4], using the euclidean distance instead of the proposed great-circle distance. The distance between the central line of the pipe and the circle center gets related to the pipe radius.

² The creation of the path through the installation space is described in section 2.1.

3.2. Simulated annealing optimization

For the optimization a modified simulated annealing algorithm [5] is used. To perform an optimization the pipes need to be modified in every step. Subsequently a decision must be taken if the new solution should be accepted.

Generating a modified solution A pipe is modified by altering the position of the points of the polyline. Additional to a random modification, more sophisticated modification schemes can be used to reach a better solution faster. A bend can, for example, be moved along its beginning and end directions, can be moved on its symmetry plane or rotated around an axis through its start and endpoint. The coordinates of the points p can be $p_x, p_y, p_z \in \mathbb{R}$.

Acceptance of a solution The decision, if a solution is accepted, is based on the evaluation value in the actual simulation step v_n and on the evaluation value in the previous simulation step v_{n-1} . A solution will be accepted if $v_n < v_{n-1}$ or $v_n > v_{n-1}$ with a possibility of

$$p = e^{-\frac{v_n - v_{n-1}}{v_{n-1} \cdot t_n}}. \quad (2)$$

As a result of this, also poor solutions can be temporarily accepted to leave a local optimum. It is possible to prohibit the acceptance of a solution if a solution is known which does not collide with the obstacles and/or with the other pipes. The temperature t_n in the current optimization step of the simulated annealing algorithm, referring to *Weyland 2008* [6], is calculated based on a initial temperature t_0 and a factor k powered by the optimization step using

$$t_n = t_0 \cdot k^n \geq 0. \quad (3)$$

The factor k is calculated based on the desired start temperature t_0 , the desired end temperature t_{end} and the user given number of optimization steps n_{steps} .

$$k = \left(\frac{t_{end}}{t_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{n_{steps}}} \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

While $t_n > 0$, an acceptance of a poor result is temporarily possible. In the progress of the optimization p should be decreased. This ensures that to the end of the optimization the algorithm behaves increasingly like a hill climbing algorithm to make it certain that the final solution is the best possible solution in the specific area of the solution space.

3.3. Selection of number of bends and optimization

The optimal number of bends for a pipe depends on the installation space as well as from the position of the start- and the end-point with their respective tangents, the bending radius, the user defined weighting of the evaluation criteria and other paths which could be intersected. Because of the combinatorial multitude of pipe sequences (in theory the piping problem is NP-complete [7]) a reliable estimation method is not known at the moment. Hence all pipe paths generated with the method described in section 2.4 are optimized in a first step. The results of this first optimization are ranked and the best paths are selected. The number of bends is determined accordingly. These paths get optimized eventually and usually with more optimization steps than the optimization in the first step was performed with. However, these optimizations can be done in parallel.

4. Validation of the pipes and final result

In order to validate whether all pipes meet the said requirements (manufacturing, clearance, collision avoidance), a renewed boundary exploration using a 3D mesh to mesh collision algorithm is performed. The requirements, which are imposed by the manufacturing constraints, are repeatedly checked in the optimization process. It can thus be assumed that these are fulfilled. Afterwards the results of the validation checks are stored so that the user can assess them. The pipes are exported as STEP files together with the length, the number of bends and the estimated mass of the pipe.

Figure 4: Fully automated generated (orange) and manually designed pipes (green) in an Airbus A320 mounting rack

In figure 4 an optimization result of 22 pipes with a combined length of approx. 20.7m and 150 bends in the presented installation space is shown in orange color. The fully automatic pipe generation took 4.5h on an Intel i5-4440. The manually designed original solution is shown in green color for comparison. The manually designed solution has a length of approx. 22.6m with 107 bends for the identical pipe connections. Interesting to note is that each automatically generated pipe turns out to be shorter than its manually designed counterpart.

5. Fully automated piping in the Airbus A320 main landing gear bay

The capabilities of the proposed automation approach are shown by generating pipes in an Airbus A320 main landing gear bay. The involute of the main landing gear bay and other forbidden stay out zones for the clearance of the maintenance holes have been omitted. A total number of 80 pipes with a combined length of approx. 98m and 614 bends are shown in figure 5. The generation of these pipes took about 23.5h on an AMD RYZEN 7 3700X. The shown solution is meant to be a first version of the final pipe work, which can be used as a starting point for the user to make educated decisions to reach the final solution (e.g. adding additional fixings).

(a) Overview (view in flight direction)

(b) Detail left side

(c) Detail right side

Figure 5: Fully automated pipe routing in an Airbus A320 landing gear bay

6. Conclusion

A method for a fully automatic pipe routing which automatically generates pipe designs that can be directly manufactured in a rotary draw bending process has been presented. This manufacturing process requires a pipe consisting of straights and bends in alternating order with specific angles and minimal lengths. Only the start and end positions with the respective direction, the pipe diameter and the properties of the intended bending machine need to be set. Also minimal distances of the pipes to obstacles and to each other can be predetermined.

An existing wire harness routing plugin of the Design Cockpit 43[®] [3] was used to find a route through the installation space. Based on this route, ray tests are performed to obtain a simplified obstacle geometry. Based on this, pipes with different number of bends are estimated. These pipes are optimized with a simulated annealing algorithm, including a just in time assessment of the constraints. The best ones are selected to be shown to the user. For the optimization an evaluation function is proposed, which takes into account multiple different criteria like the length of the pipe and the number of bends. If it occurs that several pipes are too close to each other, these pipes may be grouped and optimized together. The evaluation criteria are weighted

by the user, keeping the user in charge of the overall design decisions. Subsequently to the design optimization, the generated pipes can be automatically reviewed based on the manufacturing requirements and constraints. The capabilities of this approach are demonstrated and compared to the series pipe work in an Airbus A320 main landing gear bay.

7. Prospects

The automated piping algorithm shown forms a machine-executable, repeatable and reliable basis for a future overall optimization of a highly complex installation space as shown in figure 5 compared to the manually created A320 series solution shown in figure 6. The automation approach shown has thus the potential to reduce the pipe design effort by one to several orders of magnitude. Furthermore, the fully automated piping allows to permanently shift the focus from a detailed, microscopic view on an optimal individual pipe routing back and forth towards a more system level, macroscopic view on the main routes in system installation. Furthermore, any former manually very tedious investigation of alternative equipment changes can now be automatically executed and systematically analysed in very reasonable amounts of time.

Figure 6: Piping series solution in an Airbus A320 main landing gear bay (© 2021 Airbus)

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